

ML-based Optimization of Geometric Constellation Shaping for Unamplified Coherent Optical Systems

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ABSTRACT With increasingly higher data rate requirements imposed on short-reach links, coherent optical systems are expanding to shorter distances. To achieve a cost-efficient and low-complexity solution, optical amplifiers can be removed, enabling the deployment of the already standardized use of unamplified coherent links. However, the system performance is now governed by a peak power constraint, and therefore the conventional constellations become sub-optimal.

We will present how an end-to-end machine learning algorithm can optimize the constellation geometry. We also show the importance of a well-suited model for the channel, by experimentally comparing the performance achieved with geometries optimized for both amplified and unamplified links.

Keywords: coherent optical communications, machine learning, unamplified links

1. INTRODUCTION

As new network generations emerge, such as 6G, higher data rates are being demanded, with stringent cost and power requirements. For this reason, the current use of intensity modulation and direct detection (IM-DD) on short reach links is reaching its capacity. Coherent systems are a mature technology for their standard use on long-haul systems, that have now widespread to short reach links, owing to their robustness and tunability. To meet cost and power requirements, the use of unamplified coherent systems has been recently standardized by OIF in the 400ZR standard [1]. In these systems, no optical amplifiers are used, mitigating the use of the power-hungry and costly Erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs). However, this leads to a key paradigm change: the peak power constraint (PPC) [2]. In optically-amplified systems, the performance is mainly limited by fiber nonlinearities caused by high launched average power, which is referred to as an average power constraint (APC). Conversely, unamplified systems have low average power, and due to the lack of amplification, the limiting factor is instead the peak power at the electrical-to-optical converter. In these peak power constrained systems, it is imperative to maintain low peak-to-average power ratios (PAPRs), since a PAPR decrease is directly converted into performance gain, as we previously demonstrated [3]. For this reason, performance-enhancing advanced modulation techniques that are largely beneficial for amplified systems such as Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) probabilistic constellation shaping (PCS) require extensive optimization to be beneficial in unamplified systems due to their inherently higher PAPR [4]. With this paradigm change, it is then imperative to put at question the standard use of modulation formats, including the quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) format. Geometric constellation shaping could then be implemented, enabling the development of constellation geometries optimized for unamplified systems.

Geometric constellation shaping can be implemented with a variety of algorithms, such as the pairwise optimization algorithm [5], gradient descent [6], or making use of autoencoders (AE) [7]. Autoencoders have a widespread implementation since they enable machine learning of the entire end-to-end system, which includes the transmitter, channel and receiver, and are being used for a variety of applications and systems [8]–[10].

In this work, we make use of autoencoder-optimized geometric constellation shaping targeted at unamplified coherent systems. Recently, we experimentally demonstrated power budget gains up to 3 dB in low-order constellation formats [11], and conducted a comprehensive analysis of AE-optimized constellations for constellation sizes ranging from 8 to 128 symbols [12]. Here, we revisit our work, highlighting the implementation differences between amplified and unamplified links.

The paper is organized as follows. After this introduction, we briefly present the autoencoder structure and discuss the optimization process in section 2. Our experimental setup is presented in section 3, and experimentally-obtained results are presented in section 4. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2. MACHINE LEARNING FOR GEOMETRIC CONSTELLATION SHAPING

In this work, we implement an end-to-end machine learning algorithm to optimize the constellation geometry, which is referred to as an autoencoder (AE). A block diagram of the implemented AE is shown in Fig. 1a.

Following the approach in [7], we implement a tensorflow-based symbol-wise AE with an Adam optimizer, using the categorical cross entropy as a loss function. The AE is composed of two neural networks (NN), one at the encoder and another at the decoder, a normalization layer, and a channel.

At the encoder, given a constellation size M , a one-hot-vector is generated for the encoder input, followed by a rectified linear unit (ReLU)-activated layer and a linear-activated layer. The encoder outputs the I and Q

Figure 1: Block diagram of a) the implemented autoencoder and b) the transmitter- and receiver-side DSP blocks. c) Available constellation geometries to be loaded in the DSP.

components for the AE-optimized constellations, \mathbf{C} .

After the encoder, the I and Q components are normalized. The normalization layer is where we define if the system is average or peak power constrained. This enables the generation of constellation geometries targeting two use-cases: i) the typically deployed optically-amplified system, where the average launched power is kept constant by the optical amplifier, corresponding to the average power constraint (APC), and ii) the emerging deployment of unamplified systems, in which the modulation losses are not being compensated, and the launched power is severely dependant on the PAPR of the transmitted signal, causing a peak power constraint (PPC). Under an average power constraint (APC), each in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) component of the signal, S_I and S_Q , respectively, is divided by its average power, as given by

$$S_{I/Q} := \frac{S_{I/Q}}{\sqrt{2E[S_{I/Q}^2]}}, \quad (1)$$

where $E[\cdot]$ represents the expectation operator and $S_{I/Q}$ represents each signal component S_I and S_Q . To implement the peak power constraint (PPC), each IQ component is instead divided by its absolute maximum value,

$$S_{I/Q} := \frac{S_{I/Q}}{\max |S_{I/Q}|}, \quad (2)$$

where $|\cdot|$ represents the absolute value operator.

After the normalization layer, additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) is generated to emulate the fiber link. The fiber nonlinear behavior is not considered here, since the launched power will be low due to the lack of optical amplification.

At the decoder, after the input layer composed of the noisy IQ components, a ReLU-activated layer is implemented. The final decoder layer is composed of a *softmax* activation function to decode the received symbols.

For each constellation size, M , we generate 2×10^6 symbols, which are then divided into a number of batches. Each epoch represents a full sweep on the total amount of symbols, and both the number of epochs and batches need optimization for each M and each system constraint. Further details on the performed hyperparameter optimization can be found in our work in [12].

After conducting the offline optimization for each constellation, we collect and store the IQ mapping at the encoder output, \mathbf{C} , for each constellation size $M = \{8, 16, 32, 64\}$, and each system constraint (APC or PPC). We will refer to these AE-optimized constellations as M -AE-APC or M -AE-PPC, depending if the normalization layer enforced an average or peak power constraint, respectively. The resulting constellations are shown in Fig. 1c, together with the standard QAM format. In the coherent system, we then load \mathbf{C} at the mapper of the transmitter-side digital signal processing (DSP) block, as shown in Fig. 1b. At the receiver, the demapper implements a minimum Euclidean distance criterion, since the AE-decoder converged to a similar solution. In this manner, the complexity and latency of the coherent system are not affected.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup is depicted in Fig. 2, and the transmitter- and receiver-side DSP blocks are represented in Fig. 1b. At the transmitter, the bits are generated and mapped into constellations, including the previously

Figure 2: Experimental setup for the unamplified coherent system.

Figure 3: a) Launched optical power and b) Received constellations in optical back-to-back, for each M and constellation geometry.

AE-optimized constellations. The pulse shaper applies a root-raised cosine (RRC) function, with a roll-off of $\alpha = 0.4$ to minimize the PAPR [3]. The signal is sent to an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) operating at 120 GSa/s, and is then electrically amplified by four radio-frequency (RF) drivers before feeding the 35 GHz bandwidth dual-polarization in-phase and quadrature modulator (DP-IQM). A tunable laser source (TLS) set to a wavelength of 1554 nm and a power of 13 dBm of power is feeding the DP-IQM at the transmitter side. The communication channel is emulated by a variable optical attenuator (VOA) to account for the fiber loss. At the receiver, another TLS operating at 1554 nm and 13 dBm serves as a local oscillator (LO) for the coherent receiver that has a 40 GHz bandwidth. Four oscilloscopes with a bandwidth of 70 GHz digitize the signal at 200 GSa/s. At the receiver-side DSP, we apply Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization, which is then followed by a 4×4 constant modulus algorithm (CMA) equalizer. We then apply frequency estimation and a carrier phase estimation (CPE) with 101 taps, before the real-valued 4×4 least mean squares (LMS) equalizer. The demapper then implements minimum Euclidean distance criterion.

4. EXPERIMENTAL PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In the experimental campaign, we start by evaluating the optical launched power, evaluated at the transmitter-side, as shown in Fig. 2. Because there is no optical amplification, the launched power is particularly relevant in unamplified systems.

Figure 3a shows the measured optical power for each constellation size M and each modulation format. Overall, for AE-optimized constellations, the transmitted optical power decreases as M increases; however, for M -QAM, the power fluctuates between constellation sizes, due to the sub-optimal format of cross-QAM constellations. As expected, M -AE-PPC is generally achieving the highest launched power. For $M = 8$, 8-AE-PPC enables a power increase of 3 dB when compared to 8-QAM, owing to its reduced PAPR. From Fig. 1c, we can see that M -AE-PPC yielded the lowest PAPR for $M = 8$, achieving PAPR decreases similar to the increase in optical power. At $M = 16$, the autoencoder solution for the PPC channel converged to the standard 16-QAM, yielding equal PAPRs, and thus not achieving power gains. For $M = 32$, the QAM format is once again sub-optimal, and 32-AE-PPC is reaching a 1 dB higher launched power. With a constellation size of $M = 64$, the measured power for 64-AE-PPC and 64-QAM remains roughly the same. By comparing M -AE-PPC with M -AE-APC, we can assess the importance of adapting the normalization layer, since M -AE-PPC is enabling a 2 dB launched power increase for the majority of the constellation sizes.

The received constellations in an optical back-to-back configuration (i.e., without attenuation) are shown in Fig. 3b, and their performance is shown in Fig. 4. We evaluate the performance in terms of mutual information (MI), and assume a standard single-mode fiber (SSMF) channel with a loss of 0.2 dB/km, and ideal chromatic dispersion compensation at the receiver. Once again, larger gains are obtained at lower constellation sizes. For $M = 8$, in Fig. 4a, 8-AE-PPC enables a significant increase in range of 12.5 km when compared to 8-QAM, and 7.5 km when compared to 8-AE-APC. In Fig. 4b, 16-QAM and 16-AE-PPC yield similar distances at the

Figure 4: Achieved mutual information at different transmission distances, in an ideally-dispersion-compensated SSMF link for a) $M = 8$, b) $M = 16$, c) $M = 32$ and d) $M = 64$.

MI region of interest; however, 16-AE-PPC surpasses 16-AE-APC by 4 km. For $M = 32$, in Fig. 4c, 32-AE-PPC enables an increase of up to 6 km when compared to 32-AE-APC. Finally, for $M = 64$ in Fig. 4d, the gaussian-like geometry of the inner constellation points of 64-AE-PPC enabled an increase of range of 8 km when compared to 64-QAM, and the square geometry of the outer constellation points yielded a 5 km increase when compared to 64-AE-APC.

5. CONCLUSIONS

With the 400ZR OIF standardization paving the way towards unamplified coherent links, developing solutions well-suited for these peak power constrained (PPC) systems is imperative.

In this work, we discussed the implemented end-to-end machine learning method to achieve the optimal constellation geometry for unamplified links, highlighting the importance of an adequate normalization layer. We show AE-optimized constellations taking into account both the standard amplified, and the emerging unamplified link. We experimentally assess the performance of AE-optimized solutions and show quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) as a baseline. The AE-PPC-optimized constellations can enable significant range increase. Particularly, by adequately defining the normalization layer, AE-PPC constellations realize a transmission distance up to 7.5 km higher than geometries suited for amplified links.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was partially supported MSCA RISE programme through project DIOR (grant agreement no. 10100828) and by FEDER, through the CENTRO 2020 programme, project ORCIP (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-022141), and by FCT/MCTES through project OptWire (PTDC/EEI-TEL/2697/2021) and PhD grants SFRH/BD/143498/2019 and UI/BD/151328/2021. Fernando P. Guiomar acknowledges a fellowship from “la Caixa” Foundation (ID 100010434), code LCF/BQ/PR20/11770015.

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